

HORIZON 2020

The EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation

Data Management Plan

Deliverable D7.4

DATE

31 March 2020

ISSUE

1.0

GRANT AGREEMENT

No 870337

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU

PROJECT WEB-SITE

<http://cure-copernicus.eu/>

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document is the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the CURE project (Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe). It contains information required for the management of all data and products to be collected and generated during the project. The document outlines how data will be handled during the CURE implementation phase and after it, describing the kind of data to be collected, processed or generated, the standards to be followed and their compliance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable). A sound data management is pivotal for fully realizing CURE, as well as for allowing the wider research and user communities to access and further assess the project achievements. Within the project consortium, well curated data will stimulate and ensure smooth collaboration between the project partners. Regarding the users, sound data management will allow easy evaluation and use of the CURE data products. For dissemination, communication and exploitation purposes, open access to data generated by the project will help to underpin its credibility and stimulate the uptake of the CURE results.

The CURE DMP will evolve during the project's implementation phase. This document presents the status and planning at month 3 of the 36-month project. Updates to the provisions in this document will be recorded in the periodic update of the DMP, to take place in the middle of the project's implementation (at month 18) and in the end of the project (month 36).

1.2 Definitions and acronyms

Acronyms

CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CURE	Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
EO	Earth Observation
EMS	Emergency Management Service
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals

2 PROJECT OVERVIEW

Urban resilience refers to the ability of an urban system to maintain or rapidly return to desired functions in the face of a disturbance, to adapt to change, and to quickly transform systems that limit current or future adaptive capacity. Mitigation and adaptation actions that enhance the resilience of cities need to be based on a sound understanding and quantification of the drivers of urban transformation and settlement structures, human and urban vulnerability, and of local and global climate change, as defined in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the New Urban Agenda.

Figure 1. Conceptual illustration of CURE (Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe) development as a cross-cutting structure, based on products derived from four different Copernicus Core Services: CLMS, CAMS, C3S and EMS. The CURE system will be built on Copernicus Data and Information Access Services (DIAS) and will contain cross-cutting applications related to urban resilience, reflecting urban sustainability dimensions.

Copernicus, as the means for the establishment of a European capacity for Earth Observation (EO), is based on continuously evolving Core Services. CURE uses information from the Land Monitoring Service (CLMS), the Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS), the Climate Change Service (C3S) and the Emergency Management Service (EMS) to deal with the multidimensional nature of urban resilience and data and products - from contemporary satellite missions achieve spatially disaggregated environmental information at local (neighbourhood) and city scales

Therefore, CURE addresses urban resilience, with the development of eleven cross-cutting applications among the above Copernicus Core Services capable of coping with the required scale and granularity, by also integrating or exploiting third-party data, *in-situ* observations and modelling. CURE is introducing novel ideas on how applications for *climate change adaptation and mitigation, healthy cities and social environments*, as well as *energy and economy* will be developed across Copernicus Core Services.

3 CURE DATA OUTLINE

The CURE project will generate, collect and handle geospatial data in the format of raster (e.c. GeoTIFF), vector (e.c. shapefiles, kml/kmz), tables (e.c. csv files with coordinates and environmental parameters such as temperature, precipitation), as well as data related to the dissemination and reporting needs of the project like reports, photos, video, presentations and documents of various formats. Moreover, data from potential users will be collected in the form of questionnaires (through workshops and on-line) for the Users' Requirements Analysis. The CURE datasets can be grouped as follows:

1. Copernicus Services Data:

- a. CLMS
- b. CAMS
- c. C3S
- d. EMS

2. Copernicus Satellites Data:

- a. Sentinel 1
- b. Sentinel 2
- c. Sentinel 3

3. Third-party data:

- a. Commercial satellite data from the European Commission data warehouse
- b. Meteorological data for in-situ measurement stations

4. Questionnaires:

- a. User's requirements

5. CURE Data Products

- a. Data products from the CURE applications
- b. Data products from the CURE System

6. Reporting, Dissemination and Communication related data:

- a. Internal project reports and confidential Deliverables
- b. Dissemination and communication material (articles, conference presentations and publications, posters, leaflets,
- c. Public Deliverables

The basic data for CURE, are in Group 1, since CURE is developing cross-cutting applications from existing Copernicus Services. Therefore, large amount of data from the Copernicus Services (CLMS, CAMS, C3S and EMS) will be used. Information will also be extracted from data from the Copernicus Satellite missions (Group 2). Third-party data will be also used for algorithms calibration and validation purposes (Group 3). Data in the form of questionnaires will be collected from possible users during the workshops, of with on-line questionnaires

(Group 4). The CURE Data products (Group 5) refer to the products from the individual CURE applications, as these will be implemented for CURE case studies (see below) and the data from the CURE System, to be deposited in DIAS (Data and Information Access Services). Data for the reporting, dissemination and communication activities of the projects are also considered in Group 6. It has to be noted here, that data from Groups 1, 2, 3, 4 are data to be collected and used internally for the project implementation, while the data products from Group 5 and Group 6b and c are CURE resulting data to be made available publicly. Nevertheless, most of the data in Groups 1, 2 and 3 are also publicly available. To this end, this document will mostly focus on data from Group 5, since these are the resulting data products of the CURE project.

A range of cities with varying size are selected in CURE as case studies (Fig. 2): highly urbanized cities (Berlin, Munich) as well as typical central (Basel), western (Bristol, Vitoria-Gasteiz), northern (Copenhagen) and eastern (Ostrava, Sofia) European medium size cities, and finally a low latitude Mediterranean city with dynamic urbanization (Heraklion). Berlin, Copenhagen, Sofia and Heraklion will have the role of front runner cities, whereas the remaining ones will have the role of follower cities. In all cities, local scale and city scale CURE products will be derived from the CURE individual applications and the CURE system within DIAS (Group 5).

Indicatively, at this stage, the total size of the CURE data is estimated to be less than 2 TB.

Figure 2. The frontrunner (with blue) and the follower (with green) cities of CURE project.

4 FAIR

All the CURE data products from Group 5 and Group 6b and c will be FAIR, that is findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable. Therefore, the following sections refer to data refer to data from Group 5, since these are the resulting data products of the CURE project. It should be noted that not all details have been worked out at this point, but the CURE data management is an ongoing and evolving activity during the project.

4.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

CURE data from all Groups will be made findable, but data from Group 5 are discussed here, since these are the resulting CURE data products. Each Group 5 data product will be identified by a unique **persistent identifier** (e.c. doi) and described by rich, standardized metadata that clearly include the persistent identifier. The metadata record will be indexed in a catalog (e.c. within DIAS platform), carried with the data and will be compliant with the INSPIRE regulation. Data that will be presented in peer-review articles will become open access in open access data repositories (e.c. Zenodo, PANGAEA) if only data products will be the case. In the case of data services, these will be open access and findable in the DIAS platform. CURE products will be named following **naming conventions** of the existing Copernicus Services. For each of the new product, proper **keywords** harvested from well-established and harmonized thesaurus like EnvThes (<https://www.ecopotential-project.eu/images/ecopotential/documents/D5.6.pdf>) or GEMET (<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/en/themes/>) or other suitable vocabularies, will be used. It is expected to have more than one version of the cross-cutting applications; as such, clear **version numbers** will indicate this at the different steps. This will be indicated in the naming of each product, in the metadata file as well as in the keywords. Data from Group 5 will be associated with **metadata** files compliant with the INSPIRE regulation.

4.2 Making data openly accessible

Data from Groups 1 and 2 are already openly accessible. Data from Group 3a are not accessible since they are commercial satellite data available to CURE from the Copernicus Space Component Data Warehouse. Data from Group 3b are openly accessible by the organizations owing the in-situ measurements equipment. Data from Group 5 will be made openly accessible through DIAS. Data from Group 6b and c are openly accessible, while data from Group 6a are confidential data shared within the consortium and the EC.

The data of Group 5 will be made **openly accessible** through DIAS. The **methods** of the individual applications to be developed in CURE will be deployed in DIAS. Therefore, the only

software needed in order to access the data would be one of the DIAS platforms (yet to be decided). The respective platform provider makes the **documentation** of the DIAS platform available along with the relevant **software**. CURE will provide the associated **metadata** to all the CURE data in DIAS, as described in Section 4.1.

The CURE-System-Development Git (Bitbucket) will be used as a distributed version control system in order to store all code and documentation. Data and metadata will be stored in the DIAS Platform as described above. Experience with Git in projects is given in the existing development team and is seen qualified for the development. The usage of the services will be controlled via the user management system. Via an API there will be a user creation with a bearer authentication access to the services. All services will also need an additional license, which the user has to order. Thus, although everyone could be able to create an account, the user is not allowed to order services without a respective license for them.

4.3 Making data interoperable

CURE data of Group 5 will be interoperable and will allow data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. Most data products will be in a GeoTIFF or similar format, which allows smaller file sizes with no reduction in quality. This format is fully compliant with openly available software (like QGIS - <https://qgis.org/>) and facilitates re-combinations with different datasets from different origins.

All data will have their **metadata**; the **keywords** will be based on standardized metadata **vocabularies** like GMET (<https://www.eionet.europa.eu/gemet/en/themes/>). It is among the standard that the first version of INSPIRE metadata online editor use and is widely accepted and used among the community of Earth Observation when metadata files are created. If terms that CURE project will use, are not included or partially included, CURE will provide in the relevant technical report, the used keywords beyond GEMET vocabulary.

4.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

The open access data will be associated with specific licenses like the Creative Commons (CC); the exact type of license will be described in a next update of the DMP. The data from Group 5 will be made available for re-use immediately after their preparation, with **no embargo time** and **no restrictions**. Data from scientific publications will also be made available according to the individual embargo time of the respective publisher. A **quality assurance processes** will be followed to ensure good data quality. Each data product will be accompanied by data quality metrics, like the statistical metrics describing the accuracy, precision and uncertainty using relevant approaches.

5 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

Since the CURE project is mandated to have data and products as open access resources, unless other license is required due to data of commercial value or proprietary datasets, all costs related to that activities are foreseen in the project and covered by it. Table 1 provides an overview of the allocated resources for the CURE data storage and the respective responsible organization. Costs regarding the DIAS platform are strong connected with the development of the services and the associated data and processing expenditure. Part of the development is making the services feasible under reasonable costs and to choose the most appropriate DIAS for this project.

Table 1. Partner's indicative resources for data storage.

Organization	Data Groups	Resources
FORTH	Internal Data (Groups 1, 2, 3, 4 and 6)	1 500 €
FORTH	Data deposited on DIAS (Group 5)	5 000 €
GEOVILLE	Data deposited on DIAS (Group 5)	9 500 €

6 DATA SECURITY

All CURE data, apart from other repositories, will be secured in FORTH internal data storage facilities with daily backup. Therefore, data recovery will be possible at any time and all the data will be safely stored in for long term preservation and curation. Moreover, FORTH repositories ensures secure storage and transfer of the sensitive data from Group 4 and Group 6a. Publically available data from Group 5 will be deposited on DIAS and therefore data security in terms of recovery, storage and safety are ensured.

7 ETHICAL ASPECTS

No ethical or legal issues can have an impact on data sharing. Data from Group 4 are sensitive, since they will contain personal data, but no data from the questionnaires will be made publically available. The questionnaire data will be analyzed within CURE and information on the user requirements will be provided in Deliverable D1.1 (Summary of user requirements), which is public. It has to be noted that templates of the informed consent forms and information sheets (in language and terms intelligible to the participants) will be prepared prior to the release of the questionnaires and will be submitted as Deliverable D8.1.

8 REFERENCES

Meerow, S., Newell, J.P., Stults, M., 2016. Defining urban resilience: A review. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* 147, 38–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2015.11.011>

UN, 2015. A/RES/70/1 - Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

UN, 2017. A/RES/71/256* New Urban Agenda.

CURE Consortium Agreement.

CURE Grant Agreement, no 870337. 31/10/2019